

Non-Destructive Evaluation of 2-Mercapto Substituted Pyrimidine Derivatives in Different Concentration and Different Percentages in Dioxane-Water Mixture

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Abstract : Science and technology of ultrasonic is widely used in recent years for industrial and medicinal application. The acoustical properties of 2-mercapto substituted pyrimidines viz., 2-Mercapto-4-(2',4' -dichloro phenyl) - 6-(2' - hydroxyl -4' -methyl-5' -chlorophenyl) pyrimidine and 2 -Mercapto - 4-(4' -chloro phenyl) - 6-(2' - hydroxyl -4' -methyl-5' -chlorophenyl) pyrimidine have been investigated from the ultrasonic velocity and density measurements at different concentration and different % in dioxane-water mixture at 305K. The adiabatic compressibility (β_s), acoustic impedance (Z), intermolecular free length (Lf), apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) and relative association (RA) values have been calculated from the experimental data of velocity and density measurement at concentration range of 0.01- 0.000625 mol/lit and 70%, 75% and 80% dioxane water mixture. These above parameters are used to discuss the structural and molecular interactions.

Keywords : acoustical parameters, ultrasonic velocity, density, 2-mercapto substituted pyrimidine derivative, dioxane-water mixture

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